

FORMATION OF ABBREVIATIONS IN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article covers medical terminology and its integration relations with linguistics. Pleonastic units formed when medical terms occur in speech are analyzed. Also, the features of the formation of medical terms are classified.

Terminology (terminology and logic) — 1) 1) a branch of the lexicon; a set of terms related to the system of relevant concepts of a particular science, technology, production network, art, field of Social Activity; 2) a branch of linguistics that studies terms.

Terminology in a narrow sense refers to a specific area of Lexicon. For example, such as the terminology of physics, socio-political terminology, mechanical engineering terminology. Terminology arises on the basis of the lexicon of the universal language, becomes rich. In turn, it serves for the enrichment of the universal language. Terminological lexicon develops with it as an integral part of the lexicon of the universal language, experiencing all processes in the development of society and language. Only when a certain field or science is highly progressive does a special terminology arise in that language.

The development of terminology, ways of enrichment are different: taking words from other languages, making a new word, lexicalizing some phammatic categories, the emergence of vocabulary into a semantic whole, and the enrichment of Uzbek terminology today occurs mainly at the expense of taking words from other languages and making an internal word. The main factor determining the stability of the terminological system of this or that field is its regularity and regularity. Terminology has its own characteristics. For example, in universal language, synonymy, homonymy, and ambiguity are the richness of language, while in terminology these are negative phenomena. In particular, to express a single concept, the Uzbek term Semiconductor — Semiconductor — Semiconductor is being used. This, in turn, makes the reading-training and information sharing process difficult. For this reason, in all languages whose terminology has stabilized to some extent, terms are constantly regulated. Regulation is carried out on the basis of certain terminological norms. In the development of terminology, it is also important to publish special dictionaries related to the fields of Science[3].

In recent years, the focus has increased on the issues of the relationship of linguistics with other fields, as well as the integration of different directions with linguistics. In particular, tiblingwistics is noted as a separate branch of linguistics. "...In the new era, linguistics should remain an adjunct to other fields. Mathematical linguistics, biological linguistics, physical linguistics, medical linguistics, computer linguistics, psychological linguistics, educational linguistics, art linguistics, religious speech linguistics, orthology, etc. ... Lexicography in each area should progress on a linguistic basis... medical cooperation with linguistics is necessary. Scientific and popular variants of medical terminology should be distinguished. Medical scientific and popular text differentiation, scientific research and development of linguistic recommendations are necessary, " emphasizes Bakhtiyar Mengliyev, professor of Tashkent State University of Uzbek language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, doctor of philological Sciences [4]. This in turn causes medical speech to become a separate object of study. Today, the linguistic problems of the formation of terminological systems and the creation of field-specific terminological dictionaries are dealt with not only by linguists, but also by professional specialists, therefore, there is an inevitable integration of disciplines in practical terms. Having a conceptual apparatus of the studied field of knowledge is an important condition for achieving a high level of professional success and terminological literacy. The doctor belongs to the elite part of society, and his speech should be able to respond to normative, communicative, moral and aesthetic aspects [1].

As we all know, in the field of Medicine, abbreviations are also widely used. Abbreviations are manifested mainly in the form of the name of various diseases, medical equipment or terms. Elements of redundancy were also prominent in the study of medical abbreviations. In particular, as a result of incomplete knowledge of the meaning of the abbreviation in units such as AIDS syndrome, Orvi infection, ORC diseases, UTT examination, or neglect of the content of an abbreviation made up of initials, we witness the formation of such pleonastic compounds in the speech of doctors, diagnostic leaflets, writing disease histories. In these units, the overused unit is clearly visible when a complete explanation of the abbreviation is given:

AIDS-Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome is a virus-induced disease belonging to the retrovirus group; divided into two periods: HIV infection and the immediate AIDS period. The period of HIV infection is a period when there is a virus in the human body, but the symptoms of the disease have not yet manifested. At about the same time as the Virus in Paris, prof. Luke Montanye as well as prof in the US. Discovered by scientists led by Gallo (1983.).

"Next lesson, speaking on the topic" AIDS syndrome and its clinical signs"(Nilufar Bozorova, BukhSMI 3rd stage graduate student). In this example, the last letter in the abbreviation is the initial of the word syndrome, and this word is being re-applied both in the abbreviation and in the composition of the compound.

ARVI (acute respiratory viral infections) group. This group includes respiratory-syncytial infection, rhinovirus, adenovirus and other infections of the upper respiratory tract.

"What were the ARVI infections? I did not have time to record when they said at the lecture yesterday" (Dilrabo Ochilova, a student of the 5th stage of Bukhdti). In this case, the word governor of the compound with the initial letter in the abbreviation, as above, forms a recurrence.

ARD (Acute Respiratory Diseases) is the common name for viral – induced acute

infectious diseases of similar origin. The respiratory tract (nose, hiccups, stuttering, bronchi) is accompanied by damage to the mucous membranes, the mucous membrane of the eyes – the conjunctiva. Triggers of acute respiratory diseases include adenoviruses, paragrapp viruses, rhinoviruses, etc.

"Have you syncretized the topic of duck diseases? Give to study " (Durdona Bakhshiloyeva, Bukhdti 1st Stage Student). In this position, too, the above situation is repeated.

UTT - (ultrasound examination) is one of the newly discovered examination methods in medicine. The first ultrasound was performed only in 1956, in many areas of Medicine, in particular in obstetrics and gynecology, it has been used since the 60s of the last century[2]. B.S.From the comment in Rahimov's article, it is clarified that the second letter T in the UTT abbreviation is an abbreviation for the word examination. Despite this, in the speech of most medical workers, this abbreviation is used in pleonastic terms: "in most cases, this condition can be caused by diseases of the throat and cysts in the ovary of a teenage girl. For treatment with an accurate diagnosis, I recommend undergoing an endocrinologist examination and an UTT examination " (the answer to the question posed by the patient of the doctor-gynecologist of the higher category Gulnora Poolova).

In this example, we will not be mistaken to say that cases of neglect of the content of the abbreviation by a doctor, failure to fully understand the essence of initials in the abbreviation, in such compounds as AIDS syndrome, Orvi infection, ORC diseases, the analysis of which is presented above, caused the formation of a pleonastic unit.

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